

Design, Installation and Greenhouse Facility Evaluation of Supplemental Lighting on the Performance of Okra

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ABSTRACT

An existing greenhouse was modified for an experiment to determine the effect of supplemental lighting on the growth and development of okra. The greenhouse was divided into four plots of 0.4 m by 0.4 m each. The facilities installed in the greenhouse include 0.5 kVA solar system; lighting bulb of different wattage; drip irrigation lines; irrigation buckets and the soil pots. Lighting bulbs of 25, 65 and 100 Watts were installed. It was observed in the experiment that the plant height of okra increased with increase in time across all the wattages. The plant height also increased with an increase in the bulb wattage. Similar observation was recorded in the relationship between time and age of okra and the number of leaves. On the fruit yield of okra, the highest number of pods per plant was recorded from the plot with the highest wattage of lighting bulb of 100 watts and the number of pods decreased with an increase in the wattage of the bulb and later increased with an increase in the wattage. This result also showed that extending the period of lighting in the greenhouse had a positive influence on the weight of okra pod. It was therefore noted that morphological characteristics and yield of okra were positively influenced by extension of the day light by the supplemental lighting.

Keywords: Extension, greenhouse, lighting, okra, plant height, yield, wattage

I. INTRODUCTION

Climate change is a global issue that is not limited to a particular country and its impacts on the activities of man and his environment are now extremely felt in Nigeria. If efforts are not taken on artificial alternatives to the environmental parameters to sustain agricultural production, food production and supply crisis will continue to exist and some crops may go into extinction, especially the vegetables that are mostly consumed.

Vegetables are important crops in every home. They are consumed daily in almost every meal. Fruits and vegetables are a great source of vitamins and minerals. They contain lots of fiber and they are of low-calorie and low-fat and protect against cancer and other diseases. Fruits and vegetables help maintain good health as they are low in sodium and cholesterol (Laure[1]). All plants require light and CO₂ for photosynthesis. Most strawberry fruits in Japan are produced under forced-production culture, using June-bearing cultivars. Strawberry plants are transplanted in a heated greenhouse in autumn and the normal harvest period is from late November to June. Insufficient solar radiation for fruit loading during the winter sometimes causes a decline in growth and yield (Goto *et al.* [2])

Additional light increases the content of essential oils and other compounds in herbs and medicinal plants (Dou *et al.* [3]; Dorais and Gosselin [4]). It was further reported that Light is the driving force for photosynthesis which is plant process that changes sunlight into chemical energy. A general rule of thumb is that 1% additional light will give you a similar percentage increase in plant growth. Palaniswamy *et al.* [5] also found differences in the content of ingredients in watercress. Leaves of plants grown under 8 h photoperiod (PP) subjected to 435 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ one week before harvest, produced approx. 60 percent higher concentration of phenethyl isothiocyanate, a promising cancer inhibitor, than those that were grown continuously at 265 μmol . In general, supplemental lighting has been used not only to add artificial light to solar radiation, but also to extend the photoperiod (PP) for an increase of photosynthesis (Gomez and Izzo [6]). Temperature is also an important factor. For instance, the highest phenethyl isothiocyanate concentration in leaves and stem of watercress were produced from plant grown at 12 h PP and 25 °C in comparison to plants grown at 15 °C and 12 h PP, or plants grown at 8 h PP and either temperature (Palaniswamy *et al.* [5]). It has also been shown by studies that increasing canopy

photon capture efficiency and precisely controlling light output in response to the environment or to certain physiological parameters, energy efficiency and plant productivity can be optimized with the used of LEDs (Gomez and Izzo [6]).

Major vegetables grown in Nigeria include onion, tomato, okra, pepper, amaranthus, carrot, melon, Corchorus olitorus (ewedu), Hibiscus sabdariffa (sobo), Adansonia digitata (baobab leaves). To make the availability of these crops sustainable, efforts should be made through science and technology to prevent the reduction in their production. Therefore, this research is on the effects of supplemental lighting on the growth and performance of tropical crops.

II. METHODOLOGY AND TECHNIQUES

Experimental Site

The research site was located at the Teaching and Research Farm of Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo, Nigeria (Lat $7^{\circ} 15' N$ Long. $5^{\circ} 35' E$) and Elevation, 210m. The soil was sandy clay loam in texture

Design Analysis for the Greenhouse Facilities

The design analysis of the facilities of the greenhouse for appropriate research on supplemental lighting and crop production relationship is subsequently presented.

Area Covered by the Greenhouse and its Experimental Plots

The area covered by the greenhouse was determined as 30.33 m² using equation 1

$$\text{Area} = \text{Length} \times \text{Breadth} \quad (1)$$

The area is subdivided in four plots for the purpose of varying the forms of light and the day length. Therefore, the area of each experimental lot was determined as 7.58 m² same equation 1 above.

Material Selection and Facility Design

Wood Design and Demarcation of the Greenhouse

The greenhouse was divided into four plots of 0.4 m by 0.4 m each. Each plot (Figure 1) was demarcated using plywood with thickness of 2.5 mm. The demarcation was in order to prevent light interference among the demarcated plots. The Plywood was supported using wooden frame that consists of appropriate 50 mm x 50 mm wood.

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Figure 1: The Greenhouse for the experiment

Installation of the Solar System for Electricity Supply

An 0.5 kVA solar system (Figure 2) was installed for provision of electricity in the greenhouse. The solar system consists of a 200 W solar panel for conversion of sun energy to electrical energy, storage battery, charge controller, inverter, timer and the connection cables. A lighting point (Figure 3) of different wattage was installed in each of the demarcated plot except the control plot. The difference in wattage is to determine the effect of the wattage on the growth and development of okra as well as the proximate analysis of the okra seed.

Figure 2: The Solar Panel for Provision of Electricity in the Greenhouse

Figure 3: The lighting Bulb in the Greenhouse

Irrigation Parameters and Space Requirement

Crop Name	Okra
Plant Spacing	0.4 X 0.4 m
Number of Plants per plot	10
Irrigation System used	Bucket/Drip
Daily Evaporation/Rate	39 mm/ 1.62 mm
Irrigation Frequency used	2 times daily
Total Irrigation Time	10 minutes per frequency
Total Head	1.2 m
Length of the Lateral line	5 m
Number of Rows per Treatment	2

Figure 4: Bucket Irrigation System in the Greenhouse

Water Requirement for Okra and Selection of irrigation Bucket

The water requirement of okra was determined as 1.608 litres per day per plant using equation 1 (Ale *et al.* [7]). Therefore, for each plot, 16.08 litres of water were required per day per plot. To meet the water requirement of okra, a provision for the supply of 10 litres of water was made in each irrigation bucket twice daily for the experiment. An available bucket with calibration of 20 litres in volume was therefore selected for the experiment.

$$WR = A \times B \times C \times D \times E \tag{1}$$

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Where; WR is Water requirement (l p d /plant); A, Open Pan evaporation is 0.0274mm per day/8.3mm per year (Ale *et al.*[7]); B is Pan factor (0.7); this may differ area wise; C is Spacing of plant (m²); D is Crop factor (factor depends on plant growth-for fully grown plants = 1); E is the Wetted Area (0.3 for widely spaced crops)

The total water requirement of the farm plot would be WR x Number of Plants.

Irrigation System Design and Selection

Each plot was provided with one irrigation bucket for 2 lines (Figure 4). There were eight drippers on each bed of 2500 mm with crop spacing of 600 mm. Other features for the selection of the drippers for the okra are as follows;

Number of plants per line was 5; total number of plants in each plot is 10; water requirement per day per plant is 1.608 litres; total water requirement per day, V was 16.08 litres; total number of drippers per lateral is 8; irrigation duration(V/Q) is 10 minutes; number of drippers per experimental plot is 10.

Capacity of the Irrigation System, Q

The capacity of the irrigation system was determined as 96 litres per hour using equation 8(Sharan and Jadhav[8])

$$Q = \text{no of drippers} \times \text{drinker discharge} \quad (2)$$

Dripper discharge for non-pressure compensating on line drippers is 2-4 litres per hour.

Design and Selection of the Irrigation Laterals

According to Sharan and Jadhav [8], for a drip irrigation system in which not more than 20% of pressure variation and 10 % flow variation are desirable, the head loss(H_f) in lateral, sub-main and main lines was determined using equation 3.

$$H_f = 1.526 \times 10^4 \times \frac{Q^{1.852}}{C} \times D^{-4.873} \times L \times f \quad (3)$$

For the lateral, the discharge, Q was determined as 15 litres using equation 11.

$$Q = \frac{L_i}{S_j} \times Q_j \quad (4)$$

Roughness irrigation coefficient C.F is 140.

Allowable head loss in lateral and submain = 2 m, of this, 1.4 m is kept for head loss in lateral and 0.6 m for submain. Using equation (3) for lateral design, the Diameter of the pipe D was

determined as 7.056 mm. Minimum lateral pipe size available in market is 12 mm with internal diameter 9.8 mm. 12 mm lateral pipe was therefore selected for the laterals.

Going back to equation (3) with appropriate substitution for lateral of 12 mm, $H_f = 0.0381$ m

Sub-main Design and Selection

There are 2 laterals on one sub-main, therefore, the discharge, $Q_s = 0.016 \times 2 = 0.032 \text{ m}^3/\text{hr}$;
 $H_{fs} = 0.6$ m; $C_s = 140$

Using equation 3, the diameter of the sub-main pipe was determined as 10.43 mm. 12 mm pipe was selected for the sub-main pipes.

Installation of the Irrigation Facilities

The irrigation pipes (laterals and sub-mains), the bucket stands and the buckets were installed on a flat bed. PVC pipes of 12 mm diameter was selected based on the designs used for both the laterals and the sub-mains of the bucket stands in the greenhouse and the control plot as presented in Figure 4. There are 5 dripping points on each lateral. Each irrigation bucket (20 litres) which was manually filled supplied water to a sub-main with 2 laterals.

Cladding of the Greenhouse Cover

The greenhouse cover was installed as presented in Figure 1 with a solarig cover of 170 gsm and woven net around the sides (2000 mm) above ground level and main doors (2700 mm x 1130 mm).

Experimental Methods

The experimental test was carried out with a controlled plot outside the greenhouse for comparison among the greenhouse plots. The plant used for the experiment was okra (*abelmoschus esculentus* L. moench). The experiment was to determine the effects of supplemental lighting on the growth and performance of okra plants. The greenhouse was divided into four plots of 0.4 m by 0.4 m each. Each plot was demarcated using plywood with thickness of 2.5 mm. A lighting point of different wattage was installed in each of the demarcated plot except the control plot. The difference in wattage (25, 65 and 100 Watts) is to determine the effect of the wattage and extension of day light on the growth and performance of okra plant.

Okra plants were planted directly inside the buckets beside the dripping points of the laterals at an inter-row spacing of 60 cm and a 60 cm intra-row spacing providing 10 plants per treatment,

making 10 okra plants per plot and 40 plants in the greenhouse. The soil temperature was measured daily using soil thermometer and the morphological features of the okra plants were measured weekly to determine the variations in the growth rate of the plants per treatment. For the measurement, 3 plants were randomly selected per treatment for evaluation of the plant height, number of leaves and leaf area at the mid-flowering stage. Number of leaves were measured by manual counting and leaf area (A) was estimated using the mathematical model (equation 5) developed by Lyon [9] as reported by Agbede *et al.* [10] and Ale *et al.* [7]. The plant height was measured from the base of the plant to the shoot using a meter rule.

$$A = KL^2 \quad (5)$$

where A is the leave area; K is the constant and L is the length of the leave.

The number of fruits and fruit yield were evaluated between 5th and 7th week after planting. The fruit yields were evaluated based on the cumulative harvests per treatment. Fruits were counted and fresh weight obtained using an electronic loading balance (Superior Mini-Digital Platform Scale- China). Soil samples were collected for the particle size distribution/textural class determination.

Data Analysis

The data collected in the experiment were analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2016 to analyze the effects of supplemental lighting on the growth parameters and yield of okra;

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effects of Supplemental Lighting on the Growth Parameters of Okra

As presented in Figure 5 the plant height of okra increased with increase in time across all the wattages. The plant height of okra plant increased with an increase in the bulb wattages, showing that the height of okra plant can be influenced by heat energy. The least plant height recorded varying from 12.2 to 38 mm was observed at the plot outside the greenhouse. This also showed that the greenhouse had a lot of influence of the growth of okra plant. The maximum height of okra plant recorded was observed at the greenhouse plot with the highest wattage bulb of 100 W. This was because of the greenhouse's higher temperature as influenced by the high wattage of the lighting bulb. This is similar to the study by Akinyoola *et al.* [11] and Ale *et al.* [7] that reported that leaf number of plant increased with increase in temperature.

Similar observation was recorded in the relationship between time and age of plant and the number of leaves (Figure 6) where the number of leaves increased with an increase in the age of plants.

The stem diameter was noted with the same impact (Figure 7). The minimum diameter varied between 1.46 mm and 5.02 mm and maximum values of the stem diameter varied from 2.4 to 6.3 mm.

In the graphical analysis, APT(A) represents the greenhouse plot with 25-Watt lighting bulb; APT (B) represents the greenhouse plot with 65-Watt lighting bulb; APT (C) represents the greenhouse plot without a lighting bulb; APT (D) represents the greenhouse plot with 100-Watt lighting bulb and APT (E) represents the plot outside the greenhouse.

Figure 5: Effect of Supplemental Lighting on plant Height of okra

Figure 6: Effect of Supplemental Lighting on Numbers of leaves of okra

Figure 7: Effect of Supplemental Lighting on stem diameter of okra

Effect of the Supplemental Lighting on the Yield of Okra

The performance of okra based on the fruit yield was estimated using the number of okra pods per plant; pod weight; pod length and breadth of the pod in each experimental plot. As presented in Figure 8, the highest number of pods per plant of 3 was recorded from the plot with the highest

wattage of lighting bulb of 100 watt. In X-Y graphical analysis, the number of pods decreased with an increase in the wattage of the bulb and later increased with an increase in the wattage. (Figure 9) However, the plot outside the greenhouse had the least number of pods of 1 per stand. The maximum weight per pod (37.16 g) of okra recorded in the greenhouse was observed from the plot with the least wattage of lighting bulb of 25 Watts. While the greenhouse plot without any lighting bulb had the least weight per pod of 13.18 g and the weight per pod observed outside the greenhouse was less than the least one recorded from the greenhouse. This result indicates that extending the period of lighting in the greenhouse has a positive influence on the weight of okra pod. It can also be discussed that higher wattage of lighting bulb can result to dehydration of the okra plants. This is in conformity to Dada and Adejumo [12] that showed that the reduction in light intensity increased the numbers of fruits and leaf area.

On the size (length and breadth) of the okra fruit, Maximum values of length (24.18 mm) and breadth (17.48 mm) were recorded from the plot with the highest wattage of lighting bulb and the least values of length (11.34 mm) and breadth (7.76 mm.) were recorded from greenhouse plot without a lighting bulb. While the values observed from the plot outside the greenhouse was less than the least values from the green house, showing that Extension of the daylight and the use of greenhouse have positive influence on the yield of okra. The result is similar to Banah *et al.* [13] whose results revealed that selective spectrum in artificial lighting design can be strategically used to optimize the plant growth, development, and mineral contents uptake under controlled environments.

Figure 8: Types of Bulbs versus Number of Pods per Stand

Figure 9: Types of Bulbs versus Pod Weight

Figure 10: Types of Bulbs versus Length of pods

Figure 10: Types of Bulbs versus Length of Pod

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions were drawn from this research

1. The experiment showed that the greenhouse had much influence on the growth of okra
2. The morphological characteristics of okra plant were influenced by the supplemental lighting provided in the green house.

3. The yield of okra plant in the experiment were al so influenced by the supplemental lighting with maximum weight per pod 37.16 g as recorded from the plot with supplemental lighting.
4. There was an inverse relationship between the wattage of the bulb and the weight per pod of okra as the maximum weight per pod was recorded at plot with the least wattage.

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